

Meeting Minutes

EMA-SAWP DM: Bologna Biomechanical Computed Tomography (BBCT)

Venue: On-line Meeting

Date: 1st of September 2022, from 09:10 - 10:50

Participants:

- **QA-Applicants/Representatives:** Alessandra Aldieri (AA), Marco Viceconti (MV), Giulia Russo (GR), Valentina di Salvatore (VdS), Francesco Pappalardo (FP), Liesbet Geris (LG), Matteo Balestri (MB).
- **EMA-SAWP:** Angela Visco (AV), Flora Musuamba Tshinanu (FMT) (Coordinator, SAWP member), Elina Rönnemaa (ER) (Coordinator, SAWP member), Pieter Colin (PC) (Expert, NL), Marina Senek (MS) (Expert, SE) and Efthymios Manolis (EM) (EMA Scientific Officer)

Presentation file: pres BBCT EMA meeting Sept2022 final.pptx

EMA members started the meeting with a brief introduction. A remark from EM about which Qualification Advice (QA) documentation will be shared after the QA is completed. **QA-applicants confirmed that the decision will be taken together with EMA.**

MB started presenting with an overview of the QA submission and its purposes which are pre-competitive and aims to highlight potential issues in the regulatory qualification of drug development tools based on physics-based and physiology-based patient-specific models.

AA presented a brief overview of the BBCT methodology.

MV presented the unmet need that motivates the development of this in silico methodology. Comments from ER reminding that currently there are active control clinical trials in Osteoporosis. MV replied that even in active control trials the incidence of hip fracture rarely exceeds one percent per year of follow-up.

Comment from EM that in-silico trials should focus on bone fracture as end point, because of that there is a need to see more data.

MV continued with Context of Use (CoU) and Risk Analysis.

FMT intervened on Risk Analysis and on the problems deriving from the over-dosing or under-dosing of patients. MS agreed. MV reminded that the minimum effective dose and maximum tolerable dose would still be established experimentally.

MV continued with presenting an example of using ARF0 in a phase 2 clinical trial for a new osteoporosis treatment.

Comment from EMA-SAWP: the patient population is defined by BMD criteria and the design of the experiment in terms of dose-response instead of pair-wise comparisons.

MV continued to present the construct validity of ARF0.

FMT asked how to estimate the clinical relevance of predictor ARF0. FMT asked if it is possible to increase the predictive ability of the model by including other parameters or predictors.

MV said that since our predictor is not statistical but mechanistic, it is not so simple to add more parameters, for example the gender. FMT said that the other predictors are included in the CT scans, also height and weight of the patients. MV explained that this was already tried without success.

MV continued to present alternative clinical validation plans to address both the predictive capacity and sensitivity to change. Specifically, MV presented two new possible clinical validation plan Designs.

Comments from EMA: ER asked what second-line treatments mean; MV explained that the term is used to indicate those drugs that are prescribed when bisphosphonates are considered no more adequate; for example, Denosumab. ER also asked if after 5 years ARFO will be still evaluated. MV clarified that the ARFO is evaluated only at 0 and 12 months, coherently with the typical duration of dose-response trials

PC asked if a threshold value has been used in the two designs because it is still mentioned in the Response to list of issues document. MV clarified that in these new designs there is no need for a threshold value, as ARFO and aBMD are compared in term of their ability to discriminate the response. After the meeting the applicants checked the Response to list of issues document and they found out that the reference to the threshold was left in the reply to issues because of a clerical mistake. **A new version (v2) of Response to list of issues document was uploaded in IRIS on 2nd of September after the meeting to amend this mistake.**

FMT said that in design #2, where the study compared two different doses, there could be ethical problems that should be considered, as one of the two doses should be given off-label. ER asked if in the five years of follow up the patients would continue to be treated. MV replied affirmatively.

AA continued to present further technical details. Both ER and FMT agreed on the fact that this model could be very helpful in preventing hip fractures specially in elders. Still FMT remarked that a strong clinical validation is necessary.